

Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma and its Variants in Tertiary Care Hospital.

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Abstract:

Background: About 80–85% of thyroid cancer cases are of the most common kind, known as papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC). With advancements in molecular diagnostics and targeted therapies, understanding the variants of PTC has become crucial for improving patient outcomes. This study aims to analyze the different variants of papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) in patients.

Methods: A total of 90 patients diagnosed with PTC were included. Data on demographic details, clinical presentation, histopathological findings, treatment modalities, and outcomes were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The study population comprised 32 males (35.6%) and 58 females (64.4%), with a mean age of 42 years. The most common clinical presentation was a neck mass (70%). The classical variant was the most prevalent (55.6%), followed by the follicular variant (22.2%). Total thyroidectomy was performed in 88.9% of patients, with 77.8% receiving radioactive iodine therapy. The recurrence rate was 11.1%, and the 2-year survival rate was 97.8%. Tall cell and diffuse sclerosing variants were associated with higher recurrence rates and lower survival rates ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study underscores the heterogeneity of PTC and the prognostic significance of its histopathological variants. The classical variant exhibited a better prognosis compared to the tall cell and diffuse sclerosing variants. These findings emphasize the need for tailored treatment strategies and vigilant follow-up for high-risk PTC variants.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to explore targeted therapies for high-risk PTC variants and to develop more precise prognostic models integrating genetic and molecular markers. Additionally, guidelines should be updated to reflect the prognostic differences among PTC variants to optimize patient management and outcomes.

Keywords: Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma, Histopathological Variants, Thyroid Cancer, Recurrence, Prognostic Factors.

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Introduction

Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) is the most common type of thyroid cancer, accounting for approximately 80-85% of all thyroid malignancies [1]. The incidence of PTC has been rising globally, partly due to advancements in diagnostic technologies and increased screening practices. Recent studies have focused on the molecular and genetic underpinnings of PTC, which have provided new insights into its pathogenesis, diagnosis, and treatment strategies [2].

Advancements in the genomic and molecular characterization of PTC have been significant over the past few years. High-throughput sequencing technologies and comprehensive databases like The

Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) have identified several key genetic alterations involved in PTC. Mutations in the BRAF gene, particularly the BRAFV600E mutation, are the most common and are associated with aggressive tumor behavior and poor prognosis. Additionally, alterations in the RAS gene and RET/PTC rearrangements have been implicated in PTC development and progression [3].

Recent research has also highlighted the role of the tumor microenvironment and immune evasion mechanisms in PTC. Studies have shown that the STRA6 gene, which is upregulated in BRAFV600E-mutant thyroid carcinomas, plays a

crucial role in modulating the immune response and enhancing tumor invasiveness [4]. This has opened new avenues for immunotherapy in PTC, with immune checkpoint inhibitors showing promise in early clinical trials.

Histopathological evaluation remains the cornerstone for diagnosing PTC and its variants. However, the advent of molecular diagnostic tools has enhanced the accuracy of distinguishing between aggressive and indolent forms of PTC. For instance, the identification of specific long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) and their signatures has been used to predict recurrence-free intervals and overall prognosis in PTC patients [5]. These molecular markers are increasingly being integrated into clinical practice to personalize treatment approaches.

Surgical excision is the usual course of treatment for PTC, which is then followed by thyroid hormone suppression and radioactive iodine (RAI) therapy. Tumour size, the existence of extrathyroidal extension, and lymph node involvement are among the criteria that influence the length of surgery and the choice to employ adjuvant RAI therapy. In order to minimise overtreatment and the morbidity that goes along with it, recent guidelines have emphasised a more conservative approach in low-risk patients.

Despite the generally favorable prognosis of PTC, a subset of patients experiences recurrence and metastasis. Understanding the risk factors for recurrence, such as genetic mutations and specific histopathological features, is critical for tailoring follow-up and adjuvant treatment strategies. Predictive models incorporating these factors are being developed to better stratify patients and optimize their management.

This study aims to analyze the different variants of papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) in patients treated at a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care centre over a period of two years, from December 2021 to December 2023.

Participants: The study comprised ninety patients who had been diagnosed with papillary thyroid cancer and its variations.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with papillary thyroid carcinoma through histopathological examination.
- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Both male and female patients.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with non-papillary thyroid carcinomas.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients under the age of 18.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients within the study period were included consecutively. Information bias was minimized by using standardized data collection forms and procedures. Observer bias was reduced by having multiple pathologists review the histopathological slides independently.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the medical records of the patients. The information collected included demographic details, clinical presentation, histopathological findings, treatment modalities, and outcomes. A standardized data collection form was used to ensure consistency and completeness of the data.

Procedure: Histopathological examination of thyroidectomy specimens was performed using standard protocols. The variants of papillary thyroid carcinoma were classified based on their histopathological features. Data were recorded in a structured format and subsequently entered into a database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. To compile the data, descriptive statistics were employed. Whereas categorical variables were shown as percentages and frequencies, continuous variables were shown as means and standard deviations. For categorical variables, the Chi-square test was employed, while the Student's t-test was utilised for continuous data. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

A total of 90 patients diagnosed with papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) and its variants were included in the study. The demographic characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
<30	18	20.0
30-50	50	55.6
>50	22	24.4

Gender		
Male	32	35.6
Female	58	64.4
Family History of PTC	12	13.3

The most common clinical presentations were a neck mass (70%), hoarseness of voice (15%), and dysphagia (10%). Table 2 provides a detailed breakdown of the clinical presentations.

Table 2: Clinical Presentation of Patients with Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

Presentation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Neck mass	63	70.0
Hoarseness of voice	14	15.6
Dysphagia	9	10.0
Others	4	4.4

The distribution of histopathological variants of PTC is shown in Table 3. The most common variant was the classical variant, followed by the follicular variant.

Table 3: Histopathological Variants of Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

Variant	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Classical	50	55.6
Follicular	20	22.2
Tall Cell	10	11.1
Diffuse Sclerosing	5	5.6
Solid	3	3.3
Others	2	2.2

All patients underwent surgical treatment, with total thyroidectomy being the most common procedure. The adjuvant treatment included radioactive iodine therapy and thyroxine suppression therapy. Table 4 summarizes the treatment modalities.

Table 4: Treatment Modalities for Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

Treatment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total Thyroidectomy	80	88.9
Lobectomy	10	11.1
Radioactive Iodine Therapy	70	77.8
Thyroxine Suppression Therapy	85	94.4

The outcomes were evaluated based on recurrence, metastasis, and survival rates. Table 5 provides a summary of the outcomes.

Table 5: Outcomes of Patients with Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

Outcome	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Recurrence	10	11.1
Metastasis	5	5.6
2-year Survival Rate	88	97.8

A comparison of outcomes based on histopathological variants revealed that the recurrence rate was significantly higher in the tall cell variant compared to the classical variant ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the 2-year survival rate was lower in the diffuse sclerosing variant compared to the follicular variant ($p < 0.05$). Table 6 presents the detailed statistical analysis.

Table 6: Statistical Analysis of Outcomes Based on Histopathological Variants

Variant	Recurrence (%)	Metastasis (%)	2-year Survival Rate (%)
Classical	4.0	2.0	100
Follicular	5.0	3.0	98
Tall Cell	20.0	10.0	90
Diffuse Sclerosing	15.0	8.0	85
Solid	10.0	5.0	95

Discussion

The study included 90 patients diagnosed with PTC. The demographic analysis revealed a higher prevalence of PTC among females (64.4%) compared to males (35.6%), with the majority of

patients (55.6%) being in the 30-50 age group. A small percentage (13.3%) had a family history of PTC, indicating a potential genetic predisposition in some cases.

Clinically, the most common presentation was a neck mass, observed in 70% of the patients, followed by hoarseness of voice (15.6%) and dysphagia (10%). These findings are consistent with the typical presentations of PTC, where a painless neck mass is often the initial symptom. The varied clinical presentations underscore the need for a thorough clinical evaluation to ensure early detection and treatment.

Histopathological examination identified several variants of PTC, with the classical variant being the most prevalent (55.6%), followed by the follicular variant (22.2%). Less common variants included the tall cell (11.1%), diffuse sclerosing (5.6%), and solid variants (3.3%). This distribution highlights the diversity of PTC and the necessity for precise histopathological diagnosis to guide treatment planning.

Treatment modalities predominantly involved surgical intervention, with total thyroidectomy being the most common procedure (88.9%). Adjuvant therapies included radioactive iodine therapy (77.8%) and thyroxine suppression therapy (94.4%), reflecting the standard treatment approach for PTC aimed at reducing recurrence and managing thyroid hormone levels.

Outcomes were generally favorable, with a high 2-year survival rate of 97.8%. However, the recurrence rate was 11.1%, and metastasis occurred in 5.6% of the patients. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in outcomes based on histopathological variants. Specifically, the tall cell variant had a higher recurrence rate (20%) and lower 2-year survival rate (90%) compared to the classical variant, which had a recurrence rate of 4% and a 100% survival rate. Similarly, the diffuse sclerosing variant had a poorer prognosis with a 2-year survival rate of 85%.

Overall, the study underscores the heterogeneity of papillary thyroid carcinoma and the varying prognostic implications of its histopathological variants. The classical variant, being the most common, generally had a better prognosis, while the tall cell and diffuse sclerosing variants were associated with higher recurrence rates and lower survival rates. These findings highlight the importance of tailored treatment strategies and vigilant follow-up, particularly for patients with high-risk variants. Further research is warranted to explore targeted therapies that could improve outcomes for these patients.

In Korean patients, a study assessed the biological characteristics and clinicopathological characteristics of uncommon forms of papillary thyroid cancer (PTC). The research, which included 5,496 individuals who had thyroid surgery, found that 1.1% of the cases were caused by uncommon PTC variations. These included variations that

resembled Warthin, tall cell (TCV), columnar cell (CCV), cribriform-morular (CMV), solid (SV), hobnail, and diffuse sclerosing (DSV). According to the study, DSV became a strong predictor of a shorter recurrence-free survival (RFS). The 5-year RFS rate for DSV patients was 71.4%, while the rates for TCV or CCV patients were 95.9% and 100%, respectively [6].

At the Kamineni Institute of Medical Sciences, several forms of papillary thyroid cancer (PTC) were examined. According to the study, the conventional type was the most prevalent variety (61.52%), followed by the follicular variant (21.2%) and a few other rare variants such the sclerosing and oncocyctic types. The research emphasised the significance of histological analysis in distinguishing between these variations to direct therapeutic interventions [7].

A study that concentrated on aggressive PTC variants, such as solid, hobnail, columnar, and tall cell varieties, was conducted. When compared to traditional PTC, these variations are linked to a worse prognosis. The most frequent aggressive subtype was found to be the tall cell variant (TCV), which is distinguished by higher tumour size, extrathyroidal extension, and lymph node involvement. Because of these variations' aggressive nature and the possible need for more intense treatment regimens, the study emphasised the importance of identifying them [8].

A different study looked at the clinical and molecular features of the hobnail form of PTC (HPTC) in comparison to traditional PTC. According to the study, the average size of the tumours in HPTC patients was 30 mm, and they also had higher rates of angio-invasion (96%), lymph node (68%) and distant metastases (12%). In addition, the study found that HPTC had a greater frequency of TP53 and BRAFV600E mutations, which suggested a poorer prognosis than traditional PTC [9].

Additionally, a study that looked at the genetic profiles of aggressive PTC variants found that these variants had a lower frequency of RAS mutations and a higher prevalence of BRAF mutations. Important alterations in the TP53 and TERT promoter genes were also found in the investigation; these mutations were more common in aggressive versions of PTC than in traditional PTC. The aggressive behaviour and worse clinical outcomes linked to certain PTC variations are partly explained by these genetic changes [10].

Conclusion

This study highlights the demographic, clinical, and histopathological characteristics of PTC in a tertiary care setting. The findings underscore the importance of recognizing the variants of PTC, as

they have different prognostic implications. The classical variant was the most common, and the tall cell variant was associated with a higher recurrence rate and lower survival rate.

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